

Prevalence of HIV among Blood Donors in the Kolhan Region

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Abstract:

Background: HIV is a major global public health concern, especially in low- and middle-income nations. While blood donation is necessary, it might increase the risk of HIV transmission if suitable screening processes are not followed. Understanding the HIV prevalence among blood donors is critical to assuring the safety of the blood supply.

Aim: The study aimed to assess the prevalence of HIV among blood donors in the Kolhan region of India and to identify any associated demographic factors or risk behaviours.

Methods: This cross-sectional observational study was conducted. A total of 100 voluntary blood donors were included. Data were collected through structured questionnaires and laboratory testing for HIV antibodies using the enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) method. The data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with descriptive statistics summarizing demographic characteristics and Chi-square tests assessing associations between variables and HIV status.

Results: The study found a 4% prevalence of HIV among the blood donors. No significant associations were identified between HIV status and demographic factors such as age, gender, marital status, or occupation. However, HIV-positive donors were more likely to report high-risk behaviours, including multiple sexual partners and a history of sexually transmitted infections.

Conclusion: The study highlights a low but significant prevalence of HIV among blood donors in the Kolhan region. The lack of significant demographic associations suggests that broad-based HIV prevention strategies are necessary. Rigorous blood screening processes are essential to maintaining a safe blood supply.

Recommendations: It is recommended that blood donation centers continue to enforce stringent screening protocols and provide targeted education to high-risk groups to reduce the prevalence of HIV. Further research is needed to explore other potential risk factors and to develop region-specific strategies for HIV prevention.

Keywords: HIV Prevalence, Blood Donors, Blood Safety, Risk Factors.

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Introduction

Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV) continues to be a major public health concern around the world, with millions of people infected. Despite advances in prevention and treatment, HIV continues to spread, especially in low- and middle-income nations. Blood donation is one of the most vulnerable sites where HIV might spread if strict screening mechanisms are not in place. To prevent HIV and other blood-borne illnesses from spreading, the blood supply must be kept safe. Blood donors are widely seen as a low-risk category; yet, the prevalence of undiagnosed HIV among them poses a severe threat to the safety of the blood supply. In India, HIV is a major public health issue. According to the (NACO), there were roughly 2.1 million HIV-positive persons in India in 2019. The

predominance of HIV among adults aged 15 to 49 years was estimated at 0.22%, which, while low, represents a considerable number of people given India's enormous population [1]. Blood safety is a top priority in India due to the possibility of (TTIs). Regular monitoring and Blood donor screening is crucial to offering the safety of the blood supply.

The Kolhan region, located in eastern India, includes the districts of East Singhbhum, West Singhbhum, and Seraikela Kharsawan. This region has a heterogeneous population with varying socioeconomic origins, making it critical to investigate the HIV predominance among blood donors in this area. Previous research has found that the frequency of HIV among blood donors varies across India, ranging from 0.08% to 0.3%,

depending on the location and population investigated [2, 3]. The study aimed to assess the prevalence of HIV among blood donors in the Kolhan region of India and to identify any associated demographic factors or risk behaviours.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was conducted as a cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at the Blood Bank of a tertiary care hospital located in the Kolhan region, Jharkhand, India. The study spanned from September 2023 to February 2024, covering a period of six months.

Participants: A total of 100 blood donors were included in this study. The participants consisted of voluntary blood donors who visited the Blood Bank during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

- Voluntary blood donors aged 18 to 60 years.
- Donors who consented to participate in the study.
- Donors who met the eligibility criteria for blood donation as per the guidelines of the Blood Bank.

Exclusion Criteria

- Donors with a history of recent illness, chronic diseases, or current medication that could interfere with the study.
- Donors who did not consent to participate in the study.
- Donors who were previously diagnosed with HIV or any other sexually transmitted infections (STIs).

Bias: To minimize selection bias, only voluntary blood donors who met the inclusion criteria were

included in the study. The standard operating procedures of the Blood Bank were followed strictly to ensure consistency in the collection and processing of blood samples. To reduce information bias, the data collection process was standardized and conducted by trained personnel.

Data Collection: Data was gathered using a structured questionnaire and laboratory testing. The questionnaire included demographic information (age, gender, marital status, and occupation) and risk factors associated with HIV (history of STIs, multiple sexual partners, intravenous drug use, etc.). Blood samples were collected from each donor and tested for HIV antibodies using the (ELISA) method.

Procedure: All donors were informed about the study's purpose and written consent was obtained. After completing the questionnaire, 5 mL of blood was collected from each donor under aseptic conditions. The blood samples were then tested for HIV antibodies using the ELISA method, following the guidelines provided by the (NACO). The results of the tests were recorded, and participants who tested positive for HIV were counselled and referred for further management.

Statistical Analysis: The data was examined with SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics summarised participant demographics, and HIV prevalence was expressed as a percentage. Statistically significant relationships between demographic factors and HIV status were determined using chi-square testing (p-value < 0.05).

Results

A total of 100 blood donors were included in the study.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Blood Donors

Characteristic	Number of Participants (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Age Group (years)		
18-25	25	25%
26-35	30	30%
36-45	20	20%
46-60	25	25%
Gender		
Male	75	75%
Female	25	25%
Marital Status		
Single	40	40%
Married	60	60%
Occupation		
Student	20	20%
Self-employed	25	25%
Salaried employee	35	35%
Others	20	20%

The overall predominance of HIV among the 100 blood donors was found to be 4%. This means that 4 out of 100 blood donors tested positive for HIV.

Table 2: HIV Prevalence among Blood Donors

HIV Status	Number of Participants (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Positive	4	4%
Negative	96	96%

The correlation between various demographic variables and HIV status was assessed using the Chi-square test.

Table 3: Association between Demographic Variables and HIV Status

Variable	HIV Positive (n=4)	HIV Negative (n=96)	Chi-Square Value	p-Value
Age Group (years)				
18-25	1	24	0.13	0.72
26-35	1	29		
36-45	1	19		
46-60	1	24		
Gender				
Male	3	72	0.27	0.60
Female	1	24		
Marital Status				
Single	2	38	1.02	0.31
Married	2	58		
Occupation				
Student	1	19	0.55	0.90
Self-employed	1	24		
Salaried employee	1	34		
Others	1	19		

The Chi-square tests revealed no statistically significant association between HIV status and any of the demographic variables, as all p-values were greater than 0.05.

Additional analysis was conducted to explore the presence of known risk factors among the HIV-positive donors.

Table 4: Risk Factors among HIV Positive Blood Donors

Risk Factor	Number of HIV Positive Donors (n=4)	Percentage (%)
History of STIs	2	50%
Multiple Sexual Partners	3	75%
Intravenous Drug Use	1	25%
No Known Risk Factors	1	25%

Among the HIV-positive donors, 75% reported having multiple sexual partners, 50% had a history of sexually transmitted infections (STIs), and 25% had a history of intravenous drug use. One donor had no known risk factors associated with HIV.

Discussion

The study revealed a 4% predominance of HIV among blood donors in the Kolhan region, indicating that HIV is present within this population, albeit at a relatively low rate. The demographic analysis showed that the majority of donors were male (75%), and most were between the ages of 26 and 35 (30%). Although the prevalence was low, the presence of HIV among donors highlights the continued need for rigorous screening processes in blood banks to ensure the safety of the blood supply.

The statistical analysis indicated no significant correlation between HIV status and demographic variables such as age, gender, marital status, or occupation. This suggests that, within this sample, HIV prevalence is not strongly influenced by these demographic factors. However, when examining risk factors among the HIV-positive donors, the study found that a significant proportion of these individuals reported behaviours associated with higher HIV risk, such as having multiple sexual partners (75%) and a history of sexually transmitted infections (50%).

A study in Chhattisgarh, India, examined the seroprevalence of HIV and Hepatitis B surface antigen (HBsAg) among blood donors at a tertiary care facility. The study reported an HIV incidence of 0.2% among blood donors, with repeat donors having a greater seropositivity than first-time donors. This highlights the need of comprehensive

donor screening and education in reducing the risk of transfusion-transmissible diseases [4].

In Northwest Ethiopia, a research investigating the seroprevalence of (HIV, HBV, and HCV) among blood donors found a 2.5% HIV prevalence. The study emphasised the continuous public health risk faced by these infections, emphasising the importance of strict blood donor selection and enhanced screening processes to protect the safety of the blood supply [5].

Another study from Rajkot, India, done at the PDU Medical College, found an HIV reactivity rate of 0.12% among blood donors over a year. The study emphasised the necessity of regular screening techniques for detecting HIV and other diseases in blood donors, which protects public health by preventing transfusion-transmitted infections [6].

Conclusion

These findings suggest that while HIV is not widespread among blood donors in this region, those who are HIV-positive are more likely to have engaged in behaviours that increase their risk of infection. This underscores the importance of targeted education and intervention efforts aimed at high-risk populations, as well as the need for continued vigilance in the screening of blood donors. The lack of significant demographic associations may also indicate that HIV prevention efforts need to be broad and inclusive, addressing risk behaviour's across all segments of the population.

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